

UNIVERSITY PARTNER

Project and Professionalism (6CS007)

A2: Project Report

College Management Information System

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Abstract

College management information system is a web application with chatbot system which makes the communication network between college, teachers, students much stronger. Although conventional machine learning algorithms have been used to create chatbots, deep learning has made the dynamics of NLP simpler to model and can be used to create a chatbot that has a genuine conversation with a person. In this report, the subsystems of the application have been described in details along with problem domain and its solution. Black box testing of each function is done along with the required diagrams for developing the system.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Short Description

Information technology plays vital role in education which makes knowledge access easy and fast. College management information system is a web application which makes the communication network between college, teachers, students and parents much stronger. The system has chatbot integrated in it to help students as well as the people outside the college, to get to know about the college. There is no require for teacher to distribute heaps of handouts over hundreds of students as through this system teacher can post the handouts and access data of students. This system deals with of student, exam, curriculum, assignment details. A lot of manpower and effort is spent in the manual method. Here the system is computerized which maintains accuracy and backup easily. (Engineering Projects, 2020)

Conversation is a representation of knowledge and a primary means of communication for humans. This is why chatbots are gradually being used in a variety of domains to enable people to communicate naturally with machines when attempting to solve a particular problem. (Srivastava, et al., 2020). Based on how the chatbots are built there are two types of model: retrieval based and generative based models. In this project retrieval-based model is being used. The main technique for developing retrieval-based chatbots is response selection, which aims to choose the finest response from the collection of options considering the context of the conversation. (Gu, et al., 2019) These are the agents that have AI implanted in them and can answer user questions using NLP. A predefined knowledge base assists in the creation of an answer to the question. In a decade web has progressed from storehouse of pages for accessing static, powerful information for application development and deployment to creating dynamic application. Future development of the web application will be carried out by software engineering methods, different protocols used, application trend and web internet infrastructure (Jazayeri, 2007).

1.2 Problem Domain

Managing a large organization such as school, college has never been easier, some of the major problems faced are:

- As the number of students are high there is communication gap between teachers and the students. Teachers are not able to know about all the students and students are not able to get in touch with teachers when needed.
- The management of examination, timetable, attendance, fees manually in the bigger organization is a hassle of work.
- Requesting leave from the college is a time-consuming process. It's difficult to keep track of leave taken in journals.
- Nowadays students do not check the noticeboard as often as they need to due to which they are unaware of upcoming activities/programs organized by the college.
- It is difficult for anyone outside of the college domain to obtain information about the college.

1.3 College management information system as solution

College management system digitizes the entire operation which benefits the college in numerous ways. College management system is especially designed to save people's time and is user friendly. Some of the major use of college management system are as follows:

- Makes communication network between college, teachers, students and parents stronger as teachers can view the information of the students by a click. Teacher and student can leave feedback message to the college student service department.
- This system will convey examination, timetable, attendance, exam grades, fees information to students.
- The system allows to manage teachers and students leave as well as sanction leave requests. Teacher and student and apply for leave and the administrator can approve or disapprove the leave request.

- Students will get information about the upcoming activities/programs organized by the college with the help of chatbot.
- The college inquiry framework provides a response by summarizing the question and then extracting answers; it will also provide selective information based on the user's preferences. It will answer questions about college admissions, information on the courses, examinations.

1.4 Aims

- The College Information Management System is designed to track the performance of the education services provided by the College and to coordinate the allocation of instructional materials.
- Build a desktop application to manage the college system.
- To keep track of day-to-day activities of student and monitor improvement of student over-time.
- This system would keep students informed of college events through chatbot.
- To have a very efficient response to the user's question.

1.5 Objectives

- Monitoring and tracking student performance.
- Analyze user questions and comprehend user messages.
- To save the user's time so he or she would not have to directly go to the college for inquiries.
- The device would answer with an appropriate Interface, as if a real human is communicating to the user.
- To reduce workload on teacher by providing quick access to data of the students.

1.6 Artefacts (Proposed)

1.6.1 Functional Decomposition Diagram (FDD)

Figure 1: Functional Decomposition Diagram (FDD)

College Management Information System is divided in seven subsystems. They are user management system, attendance management system, leave management system, feedback management system, exam result management system, fee management system and chatbot system. Different steps are followed to complete each sub system as shown in the figure above. Working of the subsystem are explained briefly below.

- **User management system:**

There are three panel in the system i.e., admin, teacher and student panel. Admin can add teachers, students. Each user login will have different functions. Admin can edit the information of the users. The course, subject and session year is added and managed by the admin. Each user can edit their profile and change password. If one forgets their password, they can reset their password.

- **Attendance management system:**

Teacher can take attendance of student by fetching student list through subject and session year. Teacher can view and update attendance data. Student can view their attendance data and attendance chart is displayed in dashboard. Admin can also view student's attendance and bar graph is displayed in dashboard.

- **Leave management system:**

Teacher and student can apply for the leave with valid reason and date of leave. The leave status will be pending on the leave history. Admin can approve or disapprove the leave applied by teacher and student. The admin's approval or disapproval status will be shown in leave history of teacher and student. Leave chart is shown in dashboard of each panel.

- **Feedback management system:**

Teacher and student can leave a feedback message to the admin which will be displayed in feedback history. Admin can view and reply to the feedback message which will be displayed in their respective panel.

- **Exam result management system:**

Teacher can add assignment marks and exam marks by fetching student list through subject and session year. Teacher can view and update the marks. Student can view their exam marks. The marks above forty will be pass and below that will be fail.

- **Fees management system:**

Admin can add fee amount, given date and due date of each student through fee section. Students can view their fee details through the application.

- **Chatbot system:**

User can ask queries and the information regarding college programs and activities through the system. User inside or outside the college can chat with the system.

1.6.2 Justification of artefact

The college management system is a web application with chatbot integrated in it using python language and Django framework, which eases college to manage students account, academic progress result and easily convey notice to teachers and students. The system has three panel that is admin panel, teacher panel and student panel. This system uses simple UI/UX design with effective features to manage the college digitally. Chatbot makes easier to communicate with the automated system and ask queries related to the college. The use of web application is increasing day by day. Through this app student can get knowledge about their academic progress and stay connected with the college and the teachers.

1.6.3 Academic Questions

- How does College Management Information System work?
- What interface platform suit to make the system user-friendly?
- What extra features can be added to make the system functional?
- Which algorithm is used in chatbot?
- How can chatbot be implemented in the system?
- What are the different tools and techniques used to complete the system?
- How can College management system be made effective?

1.6.4 Academic question in detail

Explain the working of the college management information system. Explain the algorithm used to build the chatbot. Explain how was the data collected to train the chatbot. Describe the features in the system. How was the model developed while training the chatbot? Which programming language and the framework has been used to develop the system and why? Explain about the different tools and techniques used to complete the system and its importance. How was the chatbot implemented in the system? Explain about the extra features that can be added in the system to make it more effective.

1.6.5 Scope and Limitation of the project

- College management information system is an application used by universities and colleges to handle student records.
- The system allows to take and view attendance, payment details, leave apply, leave feedback message, view exam results and to view students and teacher's personal details.
- It will answer questions about college admissions, information on the courses, examinations. Both user of inside and outside of the college can ask their queries through chatbot.
- The digital presence of such programs is one of their shortcomings and drawbacks. High protection is required to protect financial records, as well as other contact information of students.
- Personal information security is a severe liability that is severely penalized by the legislation.
- Another limitation is the storage space required for the number of students. More the students, the more data is needed, and the more data, the more server computing capacity and memory are needed.

1.6.6 Report Structure

- **Chapter One: Introduction**

The introduction part presents the brief description of the system along with description of artificial intelligence and chatbot. It presents the problem domain of the system, aims and objective of the project, academic questions. Along with academic questions it views the concept of the system as solution. It also contains brief description of proposed artefacts and its justification. The scope and limitation of the project is also described in this part.

- **Chapter Two: Literature Review**

Chapter two presents the research paper and review on the similar system along with analysis and its comparison with the system. The proposed algorithm for chatbot is also described in this part. The unique selling proposition is represented using key findings along with context diagram and event list.

- **Chapter Three: Project Methodology**

This chapter comprises of the considered methodology along with its reason of rejection and the use of the chosen methodology for the project.

- **Chapter Four: Different technology and tools used for the project**

This chapter explains the different tools and techniques used during the project. It also explains the used of the tools and testing framework.

- **Chapter Five: Artefact Designs**

Chapter five comprises of artefact of each subsystem along with SRS table, wireframe, activity diagram, use case diagram, data dictionary, sequence diagram, ERD along with black box testing of each system.

- **Chapter Six: Conclusion**

Chapter six comprises of answering the academic questions along with key finding of the report and future escalation.

- **Chapter Seven: Critical Evaluation**

In this section self-reflection of project is done along with management, planning and quality of sources found.

- **Chapter Eight: Evidence of Project Management**

This section consists of the log sheet signed by supervisor as an evidence of the project. This shows that the system was on track as planned in the Gantt chart.

- **Chapter Nine: Reference and bibliography / Appendices**

In this section all the reference to the research paper is given. The additional information is kept in appendices.

Wordcount from introduction to conclusion- 10794

2. Literature Review

2.1 Review on similar system

1. Tarun, et al. developed a chatbot for college use that incorporates artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP) algorithms to help students discover information quickly. It has a basic user interface that addresses questions about the test cell, enrollment, educational, user engagement and grade point average, placement cell, and other subjects. AIML files are used to store questions and answers. When a user interacts with the chat bot, the feedback is mapped to patterns in AIML files, and the corresponding answer is displayed as a reply. Reasonable Lemmas for the keywords were discovered by Lemmatization and POS labeling in order to group together the various inflected types of the terms. Path Similarity and Wu-Palmer (WUP) Similarity were used to find word similarity. Path similarity calculates the shortest number of nodes between two-word meanings, assuming a hierarchical structure such as WordNet. A log file has been maintained to store the inputs which admin can view and add response. (Lalwani, et al., 2018)
2. According to Fernando, et al. NLAST, a natural language assistant for students has android application and server platform. The android application is chatbot based on AIML (Artificial Intelligence Modelling Language) so that students can interact with system in natural language i.e., voice and text. The server platform helps professors in the evaluation of paper-based review procedures. The goal of this system is to provide teachers with resources that will assist them in evaluating students' knowledge based on the results of written exams. Chatterbots' basic information groups are called categories and they are made up of at least two elements i.e., template and pattern. The AIML programming language is built on a stimulus-response model. The chatterbot architecture consists of an Interpreter, Bot-User Interface (BUI) and an AIML database at a high degree of abstraction. The interpreter software used by the chatterbot is based on Chatter bean. It processes the user's inputs and extracts the relevant response from the bot's knowledge base. (Fernando A, et al., 2016)

3. University of Northampton – Nile

University of Northampton providing one of the leading business educations provides quality education to its student. Northampton Technical College was founded in 1924, and the University of Northampton was founded in 2005 with continuous growth after the amalgamation of a host of training colleges. There are about 14,000 students at the university, more than 1000 foreign students from more than 100 different countries enroll annually at this to take various courses so it has a user-friendly management information system (shiksha, 2020)

Discussion and understanding

University of Northampton management information system called Nile is a web-based system where student can view their activity stream, courses, calendar, grades and assignments. Students can submit their assignments through the system and get feedback from teachers. Students gets notified when new assignments are posted. Students can check plagiarism while submitting their assignment through Turnitin. This application makes international students easy to stay connected with the university as they have help and support section where students can send message to the university. Students get access to e-library with course related books through this application (University of northampton).

Figure 2: NILE Institution Page (University of northampton)

The above figure shows the institution page i.e. first page of the web application. Here the students can ask for help and support, study support. Through this they can access to their library and learning services.

Figure 3: NILE Organizations Section (*University of northampton*)

The above figure shows the organization section where student can view the different subjects enrolled in the college and can view the materials regarding it.

Figure 4: NILE courses section (*University of northampton*)

The above figure shows the course section where student can view their courses along with each course instructor and assignment related to it.

Comparison Table

Features	University of Northampton Nile	College Management Information System
Register	×	×
Login	✓	✓
Admission	×	×
Attendance	×	✓
Reports	✓	✓
Examination	✓	✓
Fee details	×	✓
Feedback Section	×	✓
Apply for leave	×	✓
Admin panel	✓	✓
Teacher panel	✓	✓
Student panel	✓	✓

Table 1: Comparison between Nile and College management information system

4. Uniglobe College MIS

A rigorous activity on career development, leadership, research, the Uniglobe college provides its student with web-based management information system. The main objective of college is building and disseminating management, science, and technology research-based knowledge. Uniglobe college MIS has four panel i.e. admin panel, teacher panel, student panel and parent panel (edusanjal, 2017).

Discussion and understanding

In this system student can check their result, attendance, fee status, assignment grades and calendar. The feature in parent panel is same as in student panel. Student/Parent can login by the ID given by college but cannot signup/register. There are many events and activities being organized which students are unaware of, so this application notifies students of the upcoming activities. The college wants parents to be informed about their children academic progress and notify about the parent meetings. Teacher can easily distribute the handouts to the students through this application. Through the application teacher can apply for leave. Teacher can easily get students details and grade each student (uniglobe ss/college).

Figure 5: MIS Login panel (*Uniglobe ss/college*)

The above figure shows the Login panel. Depending on user requirements, admin, teacher, student and parent logins have different access levels.

Figure 6: MIS Dashboard (*Uniglobe ss/college*)

The above figure shows the dashboard of Uniglobe college management system where calendar is displayed along with the comments.

Figure 7: MIS Result section (*Uniglobe ss/college*)

The above figure shows exam result section where mark-sheet of each student is displayed, search functionality is also used in this section.

Figure 8: MIS Notice Board (*Uniglobe ss/college*)

The above figure shows the notice board section of the application where student, teacher and parent can view the upcoming activities organized in the college.

Figure 9: MIS Fee Status (*uniglobe ss/college*)

The above figure shows the student fee status where student can view their debit and credit amount of the college fee along with date of fee paid.

Comparison Table

Features	Uniglobe College MIS	College Management Information System
Register	×	×
Login	✓	✓
Admission	×	×
Attendance	✓	✓
Reports	✓	✓
Examination	✓	✓
Fee details	✓	✓
Feedback Section	×	✓
Apply for leave	✓	✓
Admin panel	✓	✓
Teacher panel	✓	✓
Student panel	✓	✓

Table 2: Comparison between Uniglobe College MIS and College management information system

5. Fedena

Fedena is a multi-purpose school management system that helps to simplify the daily activities of the school without hassle and offers informative reports and 360-degree monitoring so that stakeholders may make better and quicker decisions to improve their institution's productivity. Fedena school software manages every process seamlessly and effectively, from the coordination of the parent-teacher meeting to online fee collection and test management, to bulk data management (Foradian Technologies, 2020).

Discussion and understanding

Fedena is the free version of another program of the same name for school administration. When comparing the free version to the paid version, it becomes apparent that a number of features, including inventory, custom reports, registration, and discipline, are missing in the open-source version. This system has three panel i.e. admin panel, employee panel and student panel. Admin can edit student details, manage users, news, timetable, examinations and updates each student fee status. In employee dashboard one can edit their profile, apply for leave, get details about library, examination and human resources. In student panel, one can edit their profile, view campus news and timetable. Students get reminder of their assignment and get library due dates detail. (Darmawan, 2013).

Figure 10: Fedena Admin Dashboard (*abrarreddragon, 2017*)

The above figure shows the admin dashboard of Fedena. Through the dashboard admin can go to admission page, student details, manage users, manage news, examinations portal, timetable, attendance, setting, human resources and finance.

Figure 11: Fedena Employee Dashboard (*Foradian Technologies, 2020*)

The above figure shows the employee dashboard where the employee can view its profile, campus news, apply for leaves, view examination details, can see its library due dates and gets reminder of any important activities.

Figure 12: Fedena Student Dashboard (*Foradian Technologies, 2020*)

The above figure shows the student dashboard where one can view its profile, campus news, timetable, gets reminder of important activities, can see their academic progress and library due dates.

Comparison Table

Features	Fedena	College Management Information System
Register	×	×
Login	✓	✓
Admission	✓	×
Attendance	✓	✓
Reports	✓	✓
Examination	✓	✓
Fee details	✓	✓
Apply for leave	✓	✓
Admin panel	✓	✓
Teacher panel	✓	✓
Student panel	✓	✓

Table 3: Comparison between Fedena and College management information system

2.2 Literature review analysis

In the systems mentioned above all have admin panel and employee/teacher panel and student panel but none of the system has chatbot integrated in it. In College management information system, all three panel are included along with chatbot. Fedena has more than 500 student capacity. The main motive of Uniglobe college MIS was to ease parents to track their children academic progress through a click. In Nile, system of university of Northampton students can check plagiarism while submitting their assignment through Turnitin. Nile does not have features such as student attendance, student fee, leave applies. According to Tarun et al. as the user interacts with the chat bot, the feedback is mapped to patterns in AIML files, and the corresponding answer is displayed as a reply. From the paper published by Fernando, et al. it is known that AIML programming language is built on a stimulus-response model. The chatterbot architecture consists of an Interpreter, Bot-User Interface (BUI) and an AIML database at a high degree of abstraction. College management system is developed to help teachers to get student details easily and grade their assignment, help students track their academic progress and administrator to manage student details.

2.3 Overall comparison table

Features	Fedena	Uniglobe College MIS	University Northampton Nile	of – College Management Information System
Register	×	×	×	×
Login	✓	✓	✓	✓
Submit Assignment	×	×	✓	×
Fee status report	×	✓	×	✓
Monthly attendance report	✓	✓	×	✓
Library report	✓	×	×	×
Feedback Section	×	×	×	✓
Apply for leave	✓	✓	×	✓
Chatbot	×	×	×	✓

Table 4: Overall comparison between the similar system

2.4 Proposed Algorithm

Retrieval based model based on artificial intelligence has been used to build chatbot in this system. A database of predefined responses is maintained by a retrieval-based method. Retrieval-based bots operate on the theory of directed flows or graphs. Essentially, such bots are trained to evaluate the best answer from a limited set of predefined answers. Keras is a lightweight Python library for deep learning. In this case, a Deep Learning algorithm called Sequential from Keras is used to implement the model. In order to improve precision, a data set is generated manually. Since the mechanism is retrieval-based, it operates primarily on a closed domain. The dataset used is a collection of JavaScript objects that list various tags that refer to various types of word patterns and is stored as a Json file that contains the intents. Following the development of the dataset, various preprocessing activities are carried out in order to clean the data. When working with any NLP operation, the preprocessing task is referred to as an essential task. Here, the data under consideration were pre-processed to delete any data that does not contain any relevant information. The Natural Language Tool Kit (NLTK) and string handling functions of Python were then used to complete the subtasks in the text preprocessing step. (Surendran, et al., 2020)

A special type of recurrent neural network (LSTM) is used to identify the group, the user's response belongs to and then a random response is chosen from a list of responses. The LSTM algorithm is ideally suited for classification techniques, data processing, and prediction based on time series data. Vector data is fed into LSTM. So, before using the LSTM algorithm, the text input is translated into vector form. Word embedding is the process of converting text data into vectors, which can be done using skip-gram. Once the text has been converted into vector form, it is transferred to the LSTM algorithm as an input for any further processing. (Pardeshi, et al., 2020)

Figure 13: System Overview (Surendran, et al., 2020)

Figure 14: Sequential model of keras (Surendran, et al., 2020)

2.5 Unique Selling Proposition

College management information system is a web-based application which will help college management, teachers, students to easily convey message to each other. The main objective of this project is to develop an application through which students can check their attendance, grades, and apply for leave when needed. Through this application student and teacher can leave message to the college with one click without going to the respective college.

- There will be altogether three panels: admin panel, teacher panel and student panel.
- In admin panel, one can use CRUD features along with verifying the leave applied by teachers and students, give fee details of each student.
- In teacher panel, one can take, edit and view attendance and grade student's exam marks.
- In student panel, one can view their attendance, grades, can edit their profile, can view their fee details.
- There will be a feedback section for both teacher and student panel.
- There will be a leave section where teachers and students can apply for leave which will be verified by the admin.
- In the login page chatbot system is integrated through which users can ask queries about the college.

2.6 Project Elaboration

2.6.1 Context Diagram

Figure 15: Context Diagram

2.6.2 Event List

1. Admin enter its username and password to login in the system.
2. If correct username and password admin gets system activity.
3. Admin can add session year.
4. Admin can add and manage subject and courses.
5. Admin can add and manage teacher according to the course/subject.
6. Admin can add and manage students.
7. Admin can add fee by fetching student by session year and course.
8. Teacher enter its username and password to login in the system.
9. If correct username and password teacher gets system activity.
10. Teacher can edit its profile and password in the system.
11. Teacher can take students attendance.
12. Teacher can view and edit attendance taken.
13. Teacher can add and update the assignment and exam marks.
14. Teacher can apply for leave through the system which will be verified by admin later.
15. Teacher can leave a feedback message to the admin.
16. Student enter its username and password to login in the system.
17. If correct username and password admin gets system activity.
18. Student can edit its profile and password in the system.
19. Student can view their attendance details.
20. Student can view their grades of the examination and assignments.
21. Student can view their fee details.
22. Student can apply for leave with valid reason which will be verified by admin later.
23. Student can leave feedback if any.
24. Admin can view attendance details.
25. Admin receives teacher/student leave details and can approve or disapprove leave request.
26. Admin receives teacher/student feedback and can reply to the feedback.
27. User can reset password if one forgets its password.
28. User can ask queries about the college through chatbot integrated in login page.

3. Project Methodology

While selecting methodology, SCRUM under Agile is best suited methodology for this system as SCRUM is the most efficient methodology. Waterfall model is inflexible for the project as it does not have back tracking mechanism which makes it difficult to respond to any changes brought in the system. Prototyping Methodology is suitable only for big projects and require more resources. Spiral model is highly customized and is complex which requires experience project manager to determine how to apply it. The cycle continues without any clear termination condition which increases the risk of not meeting the budget and schedules.

The SCRUM technique meets every requirement of the phase of app creation. Scrum processes include backlogs, sprints, scrum meetings and demos. (Faniran, et al., 2017) The principle of designing a sprint-by-sprint web application while having regular meetings with the supervisor will provide the best outcome. Frequent meetings depending on the product backlog and sprint backlog will assist in tracking and improving the success of the students (Mahalakshmi & Sundararajan, 2015). SCRUM ensures time management, stage tracking and encouragement of team activity among the members of the community, increases adaptability. With separate treatment to the traditional and innovative tasks, the overall scrum cycle can prove to be complete in sense of functionality and can accommodate changes within each iteration. The approach aims to construct a full application based on user specifications and feedback. (Srivastava, et al., 2017) Hence, for this project SCRUM methodology suits the best.

Figure 16: SCRUM (Mistry, 2017)

4. Different Technology and Tools used for the project

- **Considered Programming Language**

As the college management system is a web application python programming language will be used as without writing additional code, the syntax rules of Python allow to express concepts. It is platform independent, supports the entire range of programming paradigms (from practical to fully object oriented), enables fast integration of external software modules and comes with an open-source software library. (Straßel, et al., 2020)

Figure 18: Python programming language logo (*Bartlett , 2018*)

- **Considered Framework**

Python has many open-source frameworks and tools among which Django framework is used to make this system as Django framework allows developers to concentrate on new components of the application instead of spending time on components that are already created and has high security. It Supports MVC pattern. And provides HTTP libraries. (Chou, et al., 2013)

Figure 19: Django framework logo (*django, 2020*)

- **Considered database**

MYSQL is a structured query language which will be used to store data of the project. MySQL is a free-to-use, open-source that allows databases to be managed effectively. By default, MySQL uses unencrypted links between the client and server. MySQL has functions for encrypting and decrypting data values. It is secure, efficient and stable. (Zoratti, 2016)

Figure 20: MYSQL Logo (*Logo.wine* , 2020)

- **Considered IDE**

As for the implementation part, Visual Studio (VS) Code will be used as it offers auto-complete and IntelliSense, lining, debugging, and unit testing. It provides the ability to switch easily, including virtual environments, between Python environments (Microsoft, 2019).

Figure 21: Visual Studio Code Logo (*PratyushSawan*, 2020)

- **Black box testing:**

Black Box Testing is a testing approach that involves evaluating the features and functionality of the system without knowing the internal program code and implementation specifics. Blackbox testing method is used as this testing is done from user's perspective against external variables that may trigger program errors.

- **Considered Version Control**

GitHub is a web-based version-control and collaboration platform for software developers. It stores a project's source code and track the full history of all modifications to that code. It showcases the work as most businesses look at the GitHub profiles while looking for fresh hires for their venture. (Chatziasimidis & Stamelos, 2015)

Figure 22: GitHub Logo (*InfluxData* , 2020)

- **Jupyter notebook:**

The Jupyter Notebook is an open and free platform application that allows you collaborate and maintain documents with dynamic code, statistics, data visualization, and numerical data. It was used to train the model to build chatbot.

Figure 23: Jupyter Notebook Logo (*Jupyter*, 2021)

- **Adobe XD:**

Adobe XD is a digital design tool which is used for making prototypes, wireframe and mockups.

Figure 24: Adobe XD Logo (*Logo.wine* , 2020)

- **Draw.io:**

Draw.io is used for making work breakdown structure, functional decomposition diagram, ERD, collaboration diagram.

Figure 25: Draw.io Logo

- **Start UML:**

Star UML is used for making class diagram, sequence diagram, use case diagram.

Figure 26: Start UML Logo (*StarUML, 2021*)

- **Visual Paradigm:**

Visual Paradigm is used for making Gantt chart.

Figure 27: Visual Paradigm Logo

5.Artefact Designs

5.1 User Management System

5.1.1 Software Requirement Specification (SRS)

5.1.1.1 SRS Legend

5.1.1.2 SRS Table

Requirement Code	Requirement Description	Moscow
UM-F-1.0	The system should allow admin to login into the system.	Must have
UM-NF-1.1	The password created to be stored in hashed.	Should have
UM-UR-1.1	The system should display error message if email or password is incorrect.	Must have
UM-UR-1.2	The page redirected after login must be different for admin and users.	Must have
UM-F-2.0	The system should allow admin to add user (teacher and student).	Must have
UM-NF-2.1	The email address and username of each teacher and student must be unique.	Must have
UM-NF-2.2	The password created to be stored in hashed.	Should have
UM-UR-2.1	The system should display error message when same email address or user name of teacher/student is used.	Must have

UM-UR-2.2	The system should display success message when successfully added teacher/student.	Must have
UM-F-3.0	The system should allow admin to edit user information.	Must have
UM-UR-3.1	The system should display successfully edited user when user information gets updated.	Must have
UM-F-4.0	The system should allow admin to add course, subject and session year.	Must have
UM-UR-4.1	The system should show error message if any of the field is left unfilled.	Must have
UM-UR-4.2	The system should display successful message when course, subject, session year is added successfully.	Must have
UM-F-5.0	The system should have forgot password option.	Must have
UM-NF-5.1	The system should send password reset code to the provided email by the users.	Must have
UM-F-6.0	The system should allow users to view and edit their profile.	Must have

Table 5: SRS Table for User Management System

5.1.2 Activity Diagram

Figure 28: Activity diagram of user management system (Admin)

Figure 29: Activity diagram of user management system (User)

5.1.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 30: Use Case Diagram of User Management System

5.1.4 Wireframe

Figure 31: Admin Dashboard

Figure 32: Teacher Dashboard

Figure 33: Student Dashboard

Figure 34: Admin – Manage Session Year

Figure 35: Admin – Add Course

Figure 36: Admin – Manage Course

The screenshot shows the 'Add Teacher' page. The sidebar on the left contains the following menu items: Dashboard, Add Teacher, Manage Teacher, Add Student, Manage Student, Add Course, Manage Course, Add Subject, Manage Subject, Manage Session Year, Add Fee, Teacher Feedback, Student Feedback, Teacher Leave, Student Leave, and View Attendance. The main content area has a header 'Add Teacher' and a 'dashboard' link. Below the header is a form with the following fields: Email Address, Password, First Name, Last Name, Username, and Address. A blue 'Add Teacher' button is located at the bottom of the form.

Figure 37: Admin – Add Teacher

The screenshot shows the 'Manage Teacher' page. The sidebar on the left contains the following menu items: Dashboard, Add Teacher, Manage Teacher, Add Student, Manage Student, Add Course, Manage Course, Add Subject, Manage Subject, Manage Session Year, Add Fee, Teacher Feedback, Student Feedback, Teacher Leave, Student Leave, and View Attendance. The main content area has a header 'Manage Teacher' and a 'dashboard' link. Below the header is a table titled 'Teacher Details' with the following data:

ID	First Name	Last Name	User Name	Email	Address	Last Login	Date Join	Action
1	Niraj	Shrestha	Niraj	Niraj@gmail.com	Jamal	April 10,2020,1:46p.m	April 4,2020,1:23p.m	Edit
2	Rose	Lama	Rose	Rose@gmail.com	Thamel	April 1,2020,1:20p.m	March 10,2020,1:34p.m	Edit

Figure 38: Admin – Manage Teacher

Figure 39: Admin – Add Subject

ID	Subject Name	Course Name	Course ID	Teacher Name	Action
1	Java	BIT	1	Niraj Shrestha	Edit
2	Accounts	BBA	2	Rose Lama	Edit

Figure 40: Admin – Manage Subject

The screenshot shows the 'Add Student' page. On the left is a dark sidebar menu with options like Dashboard, Add Teacher, Manage Teacher, Add Student (highlighted), Manage Student, Add Course, Manage Course, Add Subject, Manage Subject, Manage Session Year, Add Fee, Teacher Feedback, Student Feedback, Teacher Leave, Student Leave, and View Attendance. The top header is green with 'College Management System HOD Login' and 'Logout'. The main content area has a blue header 'Add Student' and a 'dashboard' link. Below are input fields for Email Address, Password, First Name, Last Name, Username, and Address, followed by a blue 'Add Student' button.

Figure 41: Admin – Add Student

The screenshot shows the 'Manage Student' page. The sidebar menu is the same as in Figure 41, with 'Manage Student' highlighted. The main content area has a blue header 'Manage Student' and a 'dashboard' link. Below is a 'Student Details' table with columns for ID, First Name, Last Name, User Name, Email, Address, Gender, Profile Pic, Session Year, Course, Last Login, Date Join, and Action. Two student records are listed.

ID	First Name	Last Name	User Name	Email	Address	Gender	Profile Pic	Session Year	Course	Last Login	Date Join	Action
5	Lisa	Karmacharya	Lisa	Lisa@gmail.com	Thamel	Female		Jan.19,2021-Feb.14,2024	BIT	April 10,2020,1:46p.m	April 4,2020,1:23p.m	Edit
6	Kinju	Shrestha	Kinju	Kinju@gmail.com	Jamal	Female		Jan.19,2021-Feb.14,2024	BIT	April 17,2020,1:10p.m	April 4,2020,1:29p.m	Edit

Figure 42: Admin – Manage Student

5.1.5 ERD

5.1.5.1 Conceptual ERD

Figure 43: Conceptual ERD of user management system

5.1.5.2 Detailed ERD

Figure 44: Detailed ERD of user management system

5.1.6 Data Dictionary

AdminHOD

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines admin id.
Created_at	DateTimeField		Date when admin is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when admin is updated is stored in this field.

Table 6: Data dictionary for AdminHOD

Teachers

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines teacher id.
Address	TextField		This field stores the address of the teacher.
Created_at	DateTimeField		Date when teacher is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when teacher is updated is stored in this field.
Admin_id	Int	Foreign Key	Admin id is extracted from AdminHod table

Table 7: Data dictionary for Teachers

Students

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines teacher id.
Gender	CharField		This field stores the gender of the student.
Profile_pic	FileField		This field stores the profile picture of the student.
Address	TextField		This field stores the address of the student.
Course_id	Int	Foreign Key	Course id is extracted from the Courses table.
Session_start_year	DateField		The year when session will start is stored in this field.
Session_end_year	DateField		The year when session will end is stored in this field.
Created_at	DateTimeField		Date when student is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when student is updated is stored in this field.
Admin_id	Int	Foreign Key	Admin id is extracted from AdminHod table

Table 8: Data dictionary for Students

SessionYearModel

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines session id.
Session_start_year	Date		This field stores the session start date.
Session_end_year	Date		This field stores the session end date.

Table 9: Data dictionary for SessionYearModel

Courses

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines course id.
Course_name	CharField		This field stores the course name.
created_at	DateTimeField		Date when course is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when course is updated is stored in this field.

Table 10: Data dictionary for Courses

Subjects

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines course id.
Subject_name	CharField		This field stores the subject name.
course_id	Int	Foreign Key	Course id is extracted from Courses table.
Teacher_id	Int	Foreign Key	Teacher id is extracted from Teachers table
created_at	DateTimeField		Date when subject is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when subject is updated is stored in this field.

Table 11: Data dictionary for Subjects

5.1.7 Class Diagram

Figure 45: Class diagram of User Management System

5.1.8 Sequence Diagram

Figure 46: Sequence Diagram of User Management System

5.1.9 Testing

Table 12: Testing for User Management System

Test Case ID	Title	Description	Test Step	Test Data	Expected Result	Post Condition	Status
TC001	Login	Testing login for user	1. Enter email address.	Email address=" " "	Error message should be displayed.	Landing page is login.	Pass
TC002			2. Enter password.	Password=" " "			
			3. Click on login button.	Email address= admin@gmail.com Password="admin1234"	Successful login.	Landing page is dashboard.	Pass

Figure 47: Invalid Login

TC003	Logout	Testing for logout.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Admin/User should be logged in. Click on logout button. 		Successful logout.	Landing on login page.	Pass
TC004	Add teacher	Testing for adding teacher	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Enter email address Enter password. Enter first name. Enter last name. Enter username. Enter address 	Email address=" " Password=" " First Name=" " Last Name=" " Username=" " Address=" "	Error message "Failed to add teacher" should be displayed.	Landing on add teacher page.	Pass
TC005				Email address=" helly@gmail.com " Password=" helly123 " First Name=" Helly " Last Name=" Shah " Username="HellyShah" Address="Thamel"	Successful message "Successfully added teacher" should be displayed.		Pass

Figure 48: Failed to add teacher

The screenshot shows a web application interface for a College Management Information System. The top navigation bar is green and contains the text "College Management Information System HOD Login" and a "Logout" link. A dark grey sidebar on the left lists various menu items, with "Add Teacher" highlighted in blue. The main content area is titled "Add Teacher" and contains a form with the following fields: "Email address" (placeholder: "Enter email"), "Password" (placeholder: "Password"), "First Name" (placeholder: "First Name"), "Last Name" (placeholder: "Last Name"), "Username" (placeholder: "Username"), and "Address" (placeholder: "Address"). Below the form, a green banner displays the message "Successfully Added Teacher". At the bottom of the form area, a blue button labeled "Add Teacher" is visible.

Figure 49:Successfully added teacher

TC006	Update Teacher	Testing for updating teacher.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on edit button. 2. Edit to field to be updated 	Email address="helly@gmail.com " Password="helly123" First Name=" Helly " Last Name=" Shah " Username="HellyS" Address="Thamel"	Successful message "Successfully Edited Teacher" should be displayed.	Landing on manage teacher page.	Pass
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The screenshot shows a web application interface for a College Management Information System. The top navigation bar is green and contains the text "College Management Information System HOD Login" and a "Logout" link. Below this, a grey header bar displays "Edit Teacher | Username : DhirajJoshi | #ID : 12" and a "Dashboard" link. The main content area features a blue header "Edit Teacher" and a form with the following fields:

- Email address:** dhiraj@gmail.com
- First Name:** Dhiraj
- Last Name:** Joshi
- Username:** DhirajJoshi
- Address:** Jamal

Below the form, a green banner displays the message "Successfully Edited Teacher". At the bottom of the form area, a blue button labeled "Save" is visible. On the left side, a dark sidebar menu lists various system functions, with "Manage Teacher" highlighted in blue.

Figure 50: Successfully Edited Teacher

TC007	Add Student	Testing for adding student	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enter email address 2. Enter password. 3. Enter first name. 4. Enter last name. 5. Enter username. 6. Enter address 7. Enter Course 	<p>Email address=" "</p> <p>Password=" "</p> <p>First Name=" "</p> <p>Last Name=" "</p> <p>Username=" "</p> <p>Address=" "</p> <p>Course=" "</p> <p>Gender=" "</p> <p>Session Start=" "</p> <p>Session End=" "</p> <p>Profile Image=" "</p>	<p>Error message</p> <p>"Failed to add student" should be displayed.</p>	<p>Landing on add student page.</p>	Pass
TC008			<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Enter Gender 9. Enter Session Start 10. Enter Session End 11. Enter Profile Image 	<p>Email address="ishita@gmail.com "</p> <p>Password="ishita123"</p> <p>First Name="Ishita "</p> <p>Last Name=" Sharma"</p> <p>Username="IshitaSharma "</p> <p>Address=" Kalanki"</p>	<p>Successful message</p> <p>"Successfully added student" should be displayed.</p>	<p>Landing on add student page.</p>	Pass

				<p>Course="BIT "</p> <p>Gender=" Female"</p> <p>Session Start="12/22/2020 "</p> <p>Session End=" 11/16/2022"</p> <p>Profile Image=" Ishita.png"</p>			
--	--	--	--	---	--	--	--

The screenshot shows a web application interface for adding a student. The page title is 'Add Student'. The form includes the following fields and values:

- Email:** [Empty]
- Password:** [Empty] with an error message: "Please fill out this field."
- First Name:** [Empty]
- Last Name:** [Empty]
- Username:** [Empty]
- Address:** [Empty]
- Course:** BIT
- Gender:** Male
- Session Year:** 2021-01-23 to 2023-03-07
- Profile Pic:** No file chosen

The interface includes a sidebar menu with options like Dashboard, Add Teacher, Manage Teacher, Add Student (highlighted), Manage Student, Add Course, Manage Course, Add Subject, Manage Subject, Add Session Year, Add Fee, Teacher Feedback, Student Feedback, Teacher Leave, Student Leave, and View Attendance. The top navigation bar shows 'College Management Information System HOD Login' and a 'Logout' link.

Figure 51:Failed to add student

admin College Management Information System HOD Login Logout

Dashboard
Add Teacher
Manage Teacher
Add Student
Manage Student
Add Course
Manage Course
Add Subject
Manage Subject
Add Session Year
Add Fee
Teacher Feedback
Student Feedback
Teacher Leave
Student Leave
View Attendance

Add Student

Dashboard

Add Student

Email:

Password:

First Name:

Last Name:

Username:

Address:

Course:
BIT

Gender:
Male

Session Year:
2021-01-23 to 2023-03-07

Profile Pic:
Choose File No file chosen

Successfully Added Student

Figure 52:Successfully added student

TC009	Update student	Testing for updating student.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on edit button. 2. Edit to field to be updated 	Email address="ishita@gmail.com " Password=" ishita123" First Name="Ishita " Last Name=" Sharma" Username="IshitaSharma " Address=" Jamal" Course="BIT " Gender=" Female" Session Start="12/22/2020 " Session End=" 11/16/2022" Profile Image=" Ishita.png"	Successful message "Successfully updated student" should be displayed.	Landing on manage student page.	Pass
-------	----------------	-------------------------------	--	---	---	---------------------------------	------

admin

Dashboard

Add Teacher

Manage Teacher

Add Student

Manage Student

Add Course

Manage Course

Add Subject

Manage Subject

Add Session Year

Add Fee

Teacher Feedback

Student Feedback

Teacher Leave

Student Leave

View Attendance

Edit Student | Username : SamirKhan | #ID : 13

Dashboard

Edit Student

Email:
samir@gmail.com

First Name:
Samir

Last Name:
Khan

Username:
SamirKhan

Address:
Kalanki

Course:
MBA

Gender:
Male

Session Year:
2021-01-23 to 2023-03-07

Profile Pic:
Choose File No file chosen

Successfully Edited Student

Figure 53: Successfully Edited Student

TC010	Add Course	Testing for adding course	1. Enter course name.	Course Name = "BIT"	Successful message "Successfully added course" should be displayed.	Landing on add course page.	Pass
TC011	Manage Course	Testing for managing course	1. Enter the updated course name	Course Name = "BBA"	Successful message "Successfully updated course" should be displayed.	Landing on manage course page.	Pass

Figure 54: Successfully Added Course

Figure 55: Successfully Edited Course

TC012	Add Subject	Testing for adding subject	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enter subject name. 2. Select course name. 3. Select teacher 	Subject name="Java" Course name = "BIT" Teacher = "Niraj Shrestha"	Success message" Successfully added subject" should be displayed.	Landing on add subject page	Pass
TC013	Update Subject	Testing for updating subject	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click on edit button. 2. Edit the field that should be updated. 	Subject name="Java" Course name = "BIT" Teacher = "Rose Lama"	Success message" Successfully added subject" should be displayed.	Landing on manage subject page	Pass

Figure 56: Successfully Added Subject

Figure 57: Successfully Edited Subject

TC014	Add Session Year	Testing for adding session year	1. Enter session start year	Session Start Year = " "	Error message "Failed to add session" should be displayed.	Landing on add session year page.	Pass
TC015				Session End Year = " "			2. Enter session end year.
				Session End Year = "08/24/2024"			

Figure 58: Failed to Add Session

Figure 59: Successfully Added Session

TC016	Reset Password	Testing for reset password	1. Enter email address. 2. Click the link sent to the email address. 3. Enter new password. 4. Enter new password confirmation.	Email address= " rose@gmail.com " Password= "rose" Confirmation password = "rose"	Error message "password similar to username, password is too short, password is too common."	Landing on reset password page.	Pass
TC017				Email address=" rose@gmail.com " Password="Healer!123" Confirmation password="Healer!123"	Successful message "Your password has been changed"	Landing on successful message with login option.	Pass
TC018				Email address=" rose@gmail.com " Password="Healer!123" Confirmation password="healer123"	Error message "The two password fields didn't match."	Landing on reset password page.	Pass

Figure 60: Message after submitting email address for reset password

Figure 61: Error message when password is short

The screenshot shows a web form titled "College Management System" with a sub-header "Change Password". It contains two input fields: "New password:" and "New password confirmation:". Below the "New password:" field, there is a red error message: "• The two password fields didn't match." At the bottom of the form is a green button labeled "Change Password".

Figure 62: Error message when two fields doesn't match

The screenshot shows the "College Management System" header. Below it, a white notification box contains the text: "Your password has been changed! You can [Login](#) now".

Figure 63: Successful reset password

5.2 Attendance Management System

5.2.1 Software Requirement Specification (SRS)

5.2.1.1 SRS Legend

5.2.1.2 SRS Table

Requirement Code	Requirement Description	Moscow
AM-F-1.0	The system should allow teacher to take students attendance	Must have
AM-F-2.0	The system should allow teacher to select the subject and session year to fetch student.	Must have
AM-NF-2.1	Teacher should select the correct subject and the session year. Incorrect subject and session year will not display student list.	Must have
AM-F-3.0	The system should allow teacher to select attendance date after fetching the student list and take students attendance.	Must have
AM-UR-3.1	The system should provide checkbox for taking attendance for easy use.	Must have
AM-UR-3.2	Error message 'Error in saving data' is displayed if attendance date is not filled.	Must have

AM-UR-3.3	Success message 'Attendance saved' is displayed if attendance id successfully taken.	Must have
AM-F-4.0	The system should allow teacher to view and update attendance.	Must have
AM-NF-4.1	The system must validate the subject and session year filled by teacher.	Must have
AM-UR-4.1	Error message 'No attendance data found' is displayed if session year is not valid.	Must have
AM-UR-4.2	The system should display updated message 'Attendance saved' when attendance is updated.	Must have
AM-F-5.0	The system should allow students to view their attendance.	Must have
AM-UR-5.1	The system should show green color for present and red color for absent for easy use.	Should have
AM-F-6.0	The system should allow admin to view student's attendance.	Must have
AM-NF-6.1	The system must validate the subject and session year filled by admin.	Must have
AM-UR-6.1	Error message 'No attendance data found' is displayed if session year is not valid.	Must have

Table 13: SRS Table for Attendance Management System

5.2.2 Activity Diagram

Figure 64: Activity Diagram of Attendance Management System (Take Attendance)

Figure 65: Activity Diagram of Attendance Management System (View Update)

5.2.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 66: Use Case Diagram of Attendance Management System

5.2.4 Wireframe

TeacherName

College Management System | Teacher Panel Logout

Take Attendance dashboard

Take Attendance

Subject

Session Year

Fetch Student

Attendance Date :

mm/dd/yyyy

Lisa Karmacharya Kinju Shrestha

Save Attendance Data

Figure 67: Teacher – Take attendance

TeacherName

College Management System | Teacher Panel Logout

View Update Attendance dashboard

View Update Attendance

Subject

Session Year

Fetch Attendance

Attendance Date

mm/dd/yyyy

Fetch Student Data

Student Attendance :

Lisa Karmacharya [Absent] Kinju Shrestha [Present]

Save Attendance Data

Figure 68: Teacher – View Update Attendance

Figure 69: Student – View Attendance

Figure 70: Admin – View Attendance

5.2.5 ERD

5.2.5.1 Conceptual ERD

Figure 71: Conceptual ERD of Attendance Management System

5.2.5.2 Detailed ERD

Figure 72: Detailed ERD of Attendance Management System

5.2.6 Data Dictionary

Attendance

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines attendance id.
Subject_id	Int	Foreign Key	Subject id is extracted from Subjects table.
Attendance_date	DateTimeField		This field stored the attendance date.
Created_at	DateTimeField		Date when course is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when course is updated is stored in this field.

Table 14: Data dictionary for Attendance

AttendanceReport

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines attendance report id.
Student_id	Int	Foreign Key	Student id is extracted from Students table.
Attendance_id	Int	Foreign Key	Attendance id is extracted from Attendance table.

Status	Boolean		This field stores the attendance status.
Created_at	DateTimeField		Date when attendance is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when attendance is updated is stored in this field.

Table 15: Data dictionary for AttendanceReport

5.2.7 Class Diagram

Figure 73: Class Diagram of Attendance Management System

5.2.8 Sequence Diagram

Figure 74: Sequence Diagram of Attendance Management System

5.2.9 Testing

Table 16: Testing for Attendance Management System

Test Case ID	Title	Description	Test Step	Test Data	Expected Result	Post Condition Result	Status
TC019	Take Attendance	Testing for taking attendance	1. Select subject.	Subject = " Java " Session Year = "Jan.19,2021 to Feb.14,2024 Attendance date = " "	Error message "Error in saving data" is displayed.	Landing on take attendance page.	Pass
TC020			2. Select Session Year				3. Click on fetch student.

Figure 75: Error in saving attendance

Figure 76: Attendance Saved

5.3 Leave Management System

5.3.1 Software Requirement Specification

5.3.1.1 SRS Legend

5.3.1.2 SRS Table

Requirement Code	Requirement Description	Moscow
LM-F-1.0	The system should allow teacher and student to apply for leave.	Must have
LM-NF-1.1	The leave reason should not exceed 150 words.	Should have
LM-NF-1.2	The system should display pending message when user apply for leave	Must have
LM-F-2.0	The system should display teacher and student leave request in admin site.	Must have
LM-F-3.0	The system should allow admin to approve or disapprove leave apply.	Must have
LM-NF-3.1	The approved or disapproved leave apply should be displayed in user page.	Must have
LM-UR-3.1	The approved leave apply should be displayed in green and disapproved leave apply should be displayed in red color.	Should have
LM-F-4.0	The user should be able to view their leave apply history.	Must have

Table 17: SRS Table for Leave Management System

5.3.2 Activity Diagram

Figure 77: Activity Diagram of Leave Management System

5.3.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 78: Use Case Diagram of Leave Management System

5.3.4 Wireframe

Figure 79: Teacher – Leave Apply

Figure 80: Student – Leave Apply

The screenshot shows the Admin interface for the College Management System. The user is logged in as 'admin'. The main content area displays the 'Teacher Leave Apply View' page. The page includes a sidebar with navigation options, a header with 'College Management System HOD Login' and 'Logout', and a table listing two teacher leave applications. The first application is approved and the second is disapproved.

ID	Teacher ID	Teacher Name	Leave Date	Leave Message	Applied On	Action
1	1	Niraj Shrestha	2021-01-22	Test	2021-01-18	Approved
2	2	Rose Lama	2021-01-28	Test	2021-01-22	Disapproved

Figure 81: Admin – View Teacher Leave

The screenshot shows the Admin interface for the College Management System. The user is logged in as 'admin'. The main content area displays the 'Student Leave Apply View' page. The page includes a sidebar with navigation options, a header with 'College Management System HOD Login' and 'Logout', and a table listing two student leave applications. The first application is approved and the second is disapproved.

ID	Student ID	Student Name	Leave Date	Leave Message	Applied On	Action
1	5	Lisa Karmacharya	2021-02-22	Test	2021-02-18	Approved
2	6	Kinju Shrestha	2021-02-28	Test	2021-02-22	Disapproved

Figure 82: Admin – View Student Leave

5.3.5 ERD

5.3.5.1 Conceptual ERD

Figure 83: Conceptual ERD of Leave Management System

5.3.5.2 Detailed ERD

Figure 84: Detailed ERD of Leave Management System

5.3.6 Data Dictionary

LeaveReportStudent

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines student leave report id.
Student_id	Int	Foreign Key	Student id is extracted from Students table.
Leave_date	CharField		This field stores the leave date of the student.
Leave_message	TextField		This field stores the leave message of the student.
Leave_status	Boolean		This field stores the leave status of the student.
Created_at	DateTimeField		Date when leave report of student is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when leave report of student is updated is stored in this field.

Table 18: Data dictionary for LeaveReportStudent

LeaveReportTeacher

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines teacher leave report id.
Teacher_id	Int	Foreign Key	Teacher id is extracted from Teachers table.
Leave_date	CharField		This field stores the leave date of the teacher.
Leave_message	TextField		This field stores the leave message of the teacher.
Leave_status	Boolean		This field stores the leave status of the teacher.
Created_at	DateTimeField		Date when leave report of teacher is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when leave report of teacher is updated is stored in this field.

Table 19: Data dictionary for LeaveReportTeacher

5.3.7 Class Diagram

Figure 85: Class Diagram of Leave Management System

5.3.8 Sequence Diagram

Figure 86: Sequence Diagram of Leave Management System

5.3.9 Testing

Table 20: Testing for Leave Management System

Test Case ID	Title	Description	Test Step	Test Data	Expected Result	Post Condition	Status
TC021	Leave Apply	Testing for leave apply	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enter leave date. 2. Enter leave reason 	Leave Date = "04/22/2021" Leave Reason "Test"	Success message "Successfully applied for leave" is displayed	Landing on Leave apply page	Pass

Figure 87: Successfully Applied for Leave

5.4 Feedback Management System

5.4.1 Software Requirement Specification (SRS)

5.4.1.1 SRS Legend

5.4.1.2 SRS Table

Requirement Code	Requirement Description	Moscow
FBM-F-1.0	The system should allow teacher and student to leave a feedback message.	Must have
FBM-F-2.0	The system should display teacher and student feedback message in admin site.	Must have
FBM-NF-2.1	The system should display date and time of the message sent.	Should have
FBM-F-3.0	The system should allow admin to reply to the feedbacks given by teachers and students.	Must have
FBM-NF-3.1	The feedback reply should be displayed in user page.	Must have
FBM-UR-3.1	A small dialogue box should be displayed to reply to the feedbacks.	Should have
FBM-F-4.0	The user should be able to view their feedback history.	Must have

Table 21: SRS Table for Feedback Management System

5.4.2 Activity Diagram

Figure 88: Activity Diagram of Feedback Management System

5.4.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 89: Use Case Diagram of Feedback Management System

5.4.4 Wireframe

Figure 90: Teacher – Feedback Message

Figure 91: Student – Feedback Message

The screenshot shows the Admin interface for the College Management System. The user is logged in as 'admin'. The page title is 'Teacher Feedback'. The sidebar contains the following menu items: Dashboard, Add Teacher, Manage Teacher, Add Student, Manage Student, Add Course, Manage Course, Add Subject, Manage Subject, Manage Session Year, Add Fee, **Teacher Feedback**, Student Feedback, Teacher Leave, Student Leave, and View Attendance. The main content area displays a table of feedback entries:

ID	Teacher ID	Teacher Name	Message	Sended On	Reply
1	1	Niraj Shrestha	Test	Jan1,2021,4:34p.m	Test
2	2	Rose Lama	Test	Feb17,2021,2:31p.m	Reply

Figure 92: Admin – View Teacher Feedback

The screenshot shows the Admin interface for the College Management System. The user is logged in as 'admin'. The page title is 'Student Feedback'. The sidebar contains the following menu items: Dashboard, Add Teacher, Manage Teacher, Add Student, Manage Student, Add Course, Manage Course, Add Subject, Manage Subject, Manage Session Year, Add Fee, Teacher Feedback, **Student Feedback**, Teacher Leave, Student Leave, and View Attendance. The main content area displays a table of feedback entries:

ID	Student ID	Student Name	Student Session	Message	Sended On	Reply
1	5	Lisa Karmacharya	Jan.19,2021-Feb.12,2024	Test	Jan4,2021,4:34p.m	Test
2	6	Kinju Shrestha	Jan.19,2021-Feb.12,2024	Test	Feb7,2021,2:31p.m	Reply

Figure 93: Admin – View Student Feedback

5.4.5 ERD

5.4.5.1 Conceptual ERD

Figure 94: Conceptual ERD of Feedback Management System

5.4.5.2 Detailed ERD

Figure 95: Detailed ERD of Feedback Management System

5.4.6 Data Dictionary

FeedbackTeacher

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines teacher feedback id.
Teacher_id	Int	Foreign Key	Teacher id is extracted from Teachers table.
Feedback	TextField		Feedback of teacher is stored in this field.
Feedback_reply	TextField		Admin reply to feedback of teacher is stored in this field.
Created_at	DateTimeField		Date when feedback of teacher is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when feedback of teacher is updated is stored in this field.

Table 22: Data dictionary for FeedbackTeacher

FeedbackStudent

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines student feedback id.
Student_id	Int	Foreign Key	Student id is extracted from Students table.
Feedback	TextField		Feedback of student is stored in this field.
Feedback_reply	TextField		Admin reply to feedback of student is stored in this field.
Created_at	DateTimeField		Date when feedback of student is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when feedback of student is updated is stored in this field.

Table 23: Data dictionary for FeedbackStudent

5.4.7 Class Diagram

Figure 96: Class Diagram of Feedback Management System

5.4.8 Sequence Diagram

Figure 97: Sequence Diagram of Feedback Management System

5.4.9 Testing

Table 24: Testing for Feedback Management System

Test Case ID	Title	Description	Test Step	Test Data	Expected Result	Post Condition	Status
TC022	Feed back	Testing for giving feedback	1. Enter feedback message	Feedback Message	Success message "Successfully Sent Feedback is displayed	Landing on feedback page.	Pass

Figure 98: Successfully Sent Feedback

5.5 Exam Result Management System

5.5.1 Software Requirement Specification (SRS)

5.5.1.1 SRS Legend

5.5.1.2 SRS Table

Requirement Code	Requirement Description	Moscow
ERM-F-1.0	The system should allow teacher to add result.	Must have
ERM-F-2.0	The system should allow teacher to select the subject and session year to fetch student.	Must have
ERM-NF-2.1	If incorrect session year is filled, student list is not displayed.	Must have
ERM-UR-2.1	Success message 'Successfully added result' is displayed when result is saved.	Must have
ERM-F-3.0	The system should allow teacher to edit result.	Must have
ERM-NF-3.1	If incorrect session year is filled, student list is not displayed.	Must have
ERM-UR-3.1	Success message 'Successfully updated result' is displayed when result is updated.	Must have

ERM-F-4.0	The system should allow students to view their result.	Must have
ERM-UR-4.1	If mark is more than or equals to forty 'Pass' is displayed in green color. If mark is less than forty 'Fail' is displayed in red color.	Should have

Table 25: SRS Table for Exam Result Management System

5.5.2 Activity Diagram

Figure 99: Activity Diagram of Exam Result Management System

5.5.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 100: Use Case Diagram of Exam Result Management System

5.5.4 Wireframe

TeacherName

College Management System | Teacher Panel

Logout

Dashboard

Take Attendance

View Update Attendance

Add Result

Edit Result

Leave Apply

Feedback

Add Result [dashboard](#)

Add Result

Subject

Session Year

Fetch Student

Student List

Assignment Marks :

Exam Marks:

Save Result

Figure 101: Teacher – Add Result

TeacherName

College Management System | Teacher Panel

Logout

Dashboard

Take Attendance

View Update Attendance

Add Result

Edit Result

Leave Apply

Feedback

Edit Result [dashboard](#)

Edit Result

Subject:

Session Year:

Student:

Assignment Marks:

Exam Marks:

Update Result

Figure 102: Teacher – Edit Result

The screenshot displays a web interface for a student's results. At the top, a green header bar contains a user profile icon, the text 'Student Name', a hamburger menu icon, 'College Management System | Student Panel', and a 'Logout' button. Below the header, a dark grey sidebar on the left lists navigation options: Dashboard, View Attendance, Result (highlighted in blue), Fee Status, Leave Apply, and Feedback Message. The main content area is titled 'Result' and includes a 'dashboard' link. A blue header bar for the table reads 'Result'. The table below has columns for ID, Subject, Assignment Marks, Exam Marks, and Status. One row shows ID 1, Subject Java, Assignment Marks 50.0, Exam Marks 88.0, and a green 'Pass' button in the Status column.

ID	Subject	Assignment Marks	Exam Marks	Status
1	Java	50.0	88.0	Pass

Figure 103: Student – View Result

5.5.5 ERD

5.5.5.1 Conceptual ERD

Figure 104: Conceptual ERD of Exam Result Management System

5.5.5.2 Detailed ERD

Figure 105: Detailed ERD of Exam Result Management System

5.5.6 Data Dictionary

Student Result

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines student result id.
Student_id	Int	Foreign Key	Student id is extracted from Students table.
Subject_id	Int	Foreign Key	Subject id is extracted from Subjects table.
Subject_exam_marks	Float		Student's exam marks is stored in this field.
Subject_assignment_marks	Float		Student's assignment marks is stored in this field.
Created_at	DateTimeField		Date when student result is created is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when student result is updated is stored in this field.

Table 26: Data dictionary for StudentResult

5.5.7 Class Diagram

Figure 106: Class Diagram of Exam Result Management System

5.5.8 Sequence Diagram

Figure 107: Sequence Diagram of Exam Result Management System

5.5.9 Testing

Table 27: Testing for Exam Result Management System

Test Case ID	Title	Description	Test Step	Test Data	Expected Result	Post Condition Result	Status
TC023	Add Result	Testing for adding result.	1. Select subject.	Course = "BIT"	Error message "Failed to add result" should be displayed	Landing on add result page.	Pass
			2. Select Session Year.	Session Year = "Jan.19,2021 to Feb.14,2024"			
			3. Click on fetch student.	Student name = "Lisa Karmacharya"			
			4. Select student name.	Assignment Marks = " "			
			5. Enter assignment marks.	Exam Marks = " "			
TC024			6. Enter exam marks.	Course = "BIT"	Success message "Successfully added result" should be displayed		Pass
				Session Year = "Jan.19,2021 to Feb.14,2024"			
				Student name = "Lisa Karmacharya"			
				Assignment Marks = " 69 "			
				Exam Marks = "80 "			

Figure 108: Failed to Add Result

Figure 109: Successfully Added Result

TC025	Edit Result	Testing for updating result	6. Select edit result. 7. Select subject. 8. Select session year. 9. Select student name.	Course = "BIT" Session Year = "Jan.19,2021 to Feb.14,2024" Student name = "Lisa Karmacharya" Assignment Marks = " " Exam Marks = " "	Message "Please fill out this field" is displayed.	Landing on edit result page.	Pass
TC026			10. Edit the updated marks.	Course = "BIT" Session Year = "Jan.19,2021 to Feb.14,2024" Student name = "Lisa Karmacharya" Assignment Marks = "75 " Exam Marks = "80 "	Success message "Successfully updated result" should be displayed		Pass

Figure 110: Failed to Update result

Figure 111: Successfully Updated Result

5.6 Fee Management System

5.6.1 Software Requirement Specification (SRS)

5.6.1.1 SRS Legend

10.3.2.1 SRS Table

Requirement Code	Requirement Description	Moscow
FM-F-1.0	The system should allow admin to add fee details.	Must have
FM-F-2.0	The system should allow admin to select the course and session year to fetch student.	Must have
FM-NF-2.1	If incorrect session year is filled, student list is not displayed.	Must have
FM-UR-2.1	Success message 'Successfully added fee' is displayed when fee is saved.	Must have
FM-UR-2.2	Error message 'Failed to add fee' is displayed if any criteria are left unfilled.	Must have
FM-F-3.0	The system should allow admin to update fee details.	Must have
FM-UR-3.1	Success message 'Successfully updated fee' is displayed when fee is updated.	Must have
FM-UR-3.2	Error message 'Failed to update fee' is displayed if any criteria are left unfilled.	Must have
FM-F-4.0	The system should allow students to view their fee status.	Must have

Table 28: SRS Table for Fee Management System

5.6.2 Activity Diagram

Figure 112: Activity Diagram of Fee Management System

5.6.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 113: Use Case Diagram of Fee Management System

5.6.4 Wireframe

Figure 114: Admin – Add Fee

ID	Date	Due Date	Amount
1	March 1, 2021	April 10, 2021	54,000

Figure 115: Student – View Fee Details

5.6.5 ERD

5.6.5.1 Conceptual ERD

Figure 116: Conceptual ERD of fee Management System

5.6.5.2 Detailed ERD

Figure 117: Detailed ERD of Fee Management System

5.6.6 Data Dictionary

StudentFee

Fields	Data Type	Constraints	Description
id	Int	Primary key, auto-increment	Uniquely defines student fee id.
Student_id	Int	Foreign Key	Student id is extracted from Students table.
Course_id	Int	Foreign Key	Course id is extracted from Courses table.
Given_date	DateTimeField		The date when fee details was given is stored in this field.
Due_date	DateTimeField		The date before which student should clear their fee is stored in this field.
Fee_amount	float		The amount of fee student should pay is stored in this field.
Created_at	DateTimeField		Date when student fee is assigned is stored in this field.
Updated_at	DateTimeField		Date when student fee is updated is stored in this field.

Table 29: Data dictionary for StudentFee

5.6.7 Class Diagram

Figure 118: Class Diagram of Fee Management System

5.6.8 Sequence Diagram

Figure 119: Sequence Diagram of Fee Management System

5.6.9 Testing

Table 30: Testing for Fee Management System

Test Case ID	Title	Description	Test Step	Test Data	Expected Result	Post Condition Result	Status
TC027	Add Fee	Testing for adding fee	1. Select course.	Course = "BIT"	Error message "Failed to add fee" should be displayed	Landing on add fee page	Pass
			2. Select Session Year.	Session Year = "Jan.19,2021 to Feb.14,2024"			
			3. Click on fetch student.	Student name = "Lisa Karmacharya"			
			4. Select student name.	Given date = " "			
			5. Enter given date.	Due Date = " "			
			6. Enter due date.	Amount = " "			
TC028			7. Enter the amount.	Course = "BIT"	Success message "Successfully added fee" should be displayed.		Pass
				Session Year = "Jan.19,2021 to Feb.14,2024"			
				Student name = "Lisa Karmacharya"			
				Given date = "04/23/2021 "			
				Due Date = "05/06/2021 "			
				Amount = "54,000 "			

TC029	Update Fee	Testing for updating fee.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Select course. 2. Select Session Year. 3. Click on fetch student. 4. Select student name. 	<p>Course = "BIT" Session Year = "Jan.19,2021 to Feb.14,2024" Student name = "Lisa Karmacharya" Given date = " " Due Date = " " Amount = " "</p>	<p>Error message "Failed to add fee" should be displayed</p>	<p>Landing on add fee page</p>	<p>Pass</p>
TC030			<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Enter given date. 6. Enter due date. 7. Enter the amount. 	<p>Course = "BIT" Session Year = "Jan.19,2021 to Feb.14,2024" Student name = "Lisa Karmacharya" Given date = "04/23/2021 " Due Date = "05/06/2021 " Amount = "54,000"</p>	<p>Success message "Successfully updated fee" should be displayed.</p>		<p>Pass</p>

Figure 120: Failed to Add Fee

Figure 121: Successfully Added Fee

Figure 122: Successfully Updated Fee

5.7 Chatbot System

5.7.1 Software Requirement Specification (SRS)

5.7.1.1 SRS Legend

5.7.1.2 SRS Table

Requirement Code	Requirement Description	Moscow
CS-F-1.0	The system should allow the user to chat.	Must have
CS-NF-1.1	Any user outside or inside the college should be allowed to chat.	Must have
CS-NF-1.2	The system should send message to the user if answer to the queries is not available.	Must have
CS-NF-1.3	The use of symbols like !, ? should not affect the reply.	Must have
CS-UR-1.1	An easy-to-use GUI must be created such that any person with no prior experience of running a device may use it.	Should have
CS-UR-1.2	A round border chatbot should be made for the users to type in queries.	Should have

Table 31: SRS Table for Chatbot System

5.7.2 Data collection

Before beginning the development model, various reports on similar types of models were studied to determine what type of dataset would've been needed for model training. Since the proposed framework is intended to address only college-related questions, the dataset had to be prepared manually. This data has been prepared manually which was in csv format. The csv data was again translated to json format so that it could be imported for training the model. The dataset that was used can be seen as follows:

```
In [1]: import pandas as pd
```

```
In [2]: df = pd.read_csv('dataset.csv')
```

```
In [3]: type(df)
```

```
Out[3]: pandas.core.frame.DataFrame
```

```
In [4]: pd.set_option("display.max.columns", None)
```

```
In [5]: df
```

	tag	patterns__001	patterns__002	patterns__003	patterns__004	patterns__005	patterns__006	patterns__007	patterns__008	responses__001	responses__002
0	greeting	Hi	How are you	Is anyone there?	Hello	Good day	Whats up	Hii	.	Hello!	Hi there, how can I help
1	goodbye	cya	See you later	Goodbye	I am Leaving	Have a Good day	ok thanks	bye	Bye Bye	Sad to see you go 😞	Talk to you later
2	name	what is your name	what should I call you	whats your name?	Your name	Who are you?	name	tell your name	NaN	You can call your personal assistant.	I'm your assistant
3	noanswer	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	Sorry, can't understand you	Please give me more info
4	options	How you could help me?	What you can do?	What help you provide?	How you can be helpful?	What support is offered	guide me	NaN	NaN	I can guide you through the website	Help you to guide through the website
5	location	location?	where are you located at?	address?	where is the college located at?	what is it's address	NaN	NaN	NaN	We are located at Naxal, Kathmandu.	You can visit us at Naxa Kathmandu

Figure 123: Dataset visualization

5.7.3 Model Development

Figure 124: Architecture of chatbot

The steps involved while developing the model are described below.

- **Activate and import the dataset:**
At the beginning the needed packages for the chatbot are imported and the variables are initialized. For example, pickle, json, nltk, NumPy, keras, random are imported.
- **Information preprocessing:**
While dealing with textual information, we must perform multiple preprocessing steps on the data while building an artificial intelligence or deep learning model. Tokenization is the most fundamental thing done with text content. Tokenizing is the method of dividing a large text into small bits, such as sentences. In this step, it is appended via the patterns, the sentence is tokenized with the `nltk.word_tokenize()` feature, and each word is inserted in the words list.
- **Create data for training and testing:**
Now the training files are made, which will have input, output. The input will be the pattern, and output will be the class where pattern belongs. Since the machine does not understand code, it is translated into numbers.
- **Create the blueprint:**
Now a three-layered deep neural network is built using Keras sequential API. 100 percent accuracy was reached on the model after practicing it for 200 epochs. The model will only indicate the class it belongs to, some functions are

written to define the class and then extract a random answer from the set of answers.

- Predict the outcome:

For predicting the class, input must be given in same manner as given while training. After prediction of the class, some random answer is generated from the set of intents.

6. Conclusion

Chatbots are digital services that can be operated via natural language communication. They could be used via smart phones without downloading dedicated applications, and they can be integrated in websites and social networks. Retrieval based chatbot was built using keras, TensorFlow and nltk which was implemented in Django. This application will help college to maintain teacher, student information digitally. This system deals with of student, exam, curriculum, assignment, attendance, feedback and leave details. College management system is especially designed to save people's time and is user friendly.

The system has a lot of space for improvement. In future, parent panel can also be added through which parents can easily check their children academic progress and stay connected with the college. Generative based chatbot can be implemented. Using generative methods, chatbots will create new conversation from large quantities of communicative training data. This app, like most software, does have a lot of hidden bugs. During the maintenance and implementation of the application in real life the program will be upgraded and updated on a regular basis.

7. Critical Evaluation of the Project

After analyzing the entire report, it is found that incorporating Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays a significant role when developing an application, whether this is an android application or web application. The project methodology had a major influence on the project. If the appropriate methodology was not used, the project might have failed. The agile approach was crucial in ensuring that the project proceeded smoothly step by step. The first step was determining sub systems in the project. The sub systems chosen are user management system, attendance management system, leave management system, feedback management system, exam result management system, fee management system and chatbot system. Choosing and comparing different related systems made it clear to determine the elements, algorithm needed to be implemented, and the important features of the system. Creating SRS documents for each subsystem made it easier visualize and develop new functions. Designing and visualizing all artefact designs like activity diagrams, use case diagrams, erd, and class diagrams assisted in physically representing all of the data for the purpose of capturing facts, drawing plans, and improving learning and efficiency. Without Django framework, it would not be possible to progress in development as the framework has different features and dependencies were preinstalled in it. Self-study, research and analysis are very important factors to complete a project.

8. Evidence of project management

8.1 Log Sheet

1.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

 UNIVERSITY OF
WOLVERHAMPTON

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: <i>Pritisha</i>	Surname: <i>Tuladhar</i>
Student Number: <i>2040265</i>	Supervisor: <i>Sagar Khadgi</i>
Project Title: <i>College Management Information System</i>	Month: <i>September</i>
What have you done since the last meeting	
<i>First meeting 'Topic Selection Meeting'</i>	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
<i>Finalize the topic. Write the features of the system.</i>	
Supervisor comments	
<i>Select the suitable topic for your FYP and discuss the features of the system.</i>	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: *Pritisha* Date: *09/10/2020*

Supervisor Signature: *Sagar Khadgi* Date: *09/10/2020*

2.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: <i>Pritisha</i>	Surname: <i>Tuladhar</i>
Student Number: <i>2040265</i>	Supervisor: <i>Sagar Khadgi</i>
Project Title: <i>College Management Information System</i> Month: <i>September</i>	
What have you done since the last meeting	
<i>Discussed about the project title and its feature.</i>	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
<i>complete proposal writing.</i>	
Supervisor comments	
<i>Write the introduction, features of the system, methodology used, make gantt chart.</i>	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: *Pritisha* Date: *09/11/2020*

Supervisor Signature: *Sagar Khadgi* Date: *09/11/2020*

3.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG

First Name: Pritisha Surname: Tuladhar

Student Number: 2040265 Supervisor: Sagar Khadgi

Project Title: College Management Information System Month: September

What have you done since the last meeting

Discussed about the artefacts, similar system, functional decomposition diagram (FDD), Gantt chart.

What do you aim to complete before the next meeting

Complete Proposal writing.

Supervisor comments

Functional decomposition diagram must be included in the proposal. Wireframes can be added. Artefact must include how the system works. You can research about three or more similar systems. Work breakage can be done according to sprint in WBS.

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: Pritisha

Date: 09/17/2020

Supervisor Signature: Sagar Khadgi

Date: 09/17/2020

4.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: Pritisha	Surname: Tuladhar
Student Number: 2040265	Supervisor: Sagar Khadgi
Project Title: College Management Information System Month: September	
What have you done since the last meeting	
Feedback on first draft of the proposal. Completed proposal (introduction, feature of the system, methodology, gantt chart).	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
Complete the final proposal writing. Add aims and objective and unique features in the solution section. (Previous Mahy Agardos ???)	
Supervisor comments	
Objective seems more like aims. Add web growth development in introduction section. Add unique features in the solution as well. Give reference to each screenshot of similar system. Add justification of artefact. Do not use first person.	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: Pritisha

Date: 09/21/2020

Supervisor Signature: [Signature]

Date: 09/21/2020

5.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: Pritisha	Surname: Tuladhar
Student Number: 2040265	Supervisor: Sagar Khadgi
Project Title: College Management Information System Month: October	
What have you done since the last meeting	
Finished the proposal after final feedback and submitted to the portal and started further research on the topic.	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
I aim to complete the first draft of the literature review of my project review before getting feedbacks from the supervisor.	
Supervisor comments	
Start working upon the literature review as well as artefact side by side in order to submit before deadline after working on the feedbacks.	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: Pritisha

Date: 10/2/2020

Supervisor Signature: Sagar Khadgi

Date: 10/2/2020

6.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: Pritisha	Surname: Tuladhar
Student Number: 2040265	Supervisor: Sagar Khadgi
Project Title: College Management Information System Month: October	
What have you done since the last meeting	
Discussed about the first draft of literature review Worked on literature review (similar system).	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
Complete the literature review. Take survey and include it in report as well.	
Supervisor comments	
Discuss detail about the similar system. Add literature review analysis. Write description of each screenshot. Add unique selling proposition. Remove one of the similar system review. Write implementation regarding the project in different paragraph. Add numbering in context diagram.	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: Pritisha

Date: 10/08/2020

Supervisor Signature: Sagar Khadgi

Date: 10/08/2020

7.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG

First Name: *Pritisha* Surname: *Tuladhar*

Student Number: *2040265* Supervisor: *Sagar Khadgi*

Project Title: *College Management Information System* Month: *October*

What have you done since the last meeting

*Discussed about the second draft of literature review.
Added literature review analysis, unique selling proposition.*

What do you aim to complete before the next meeting

Complete the literature review. Add references in every section.

Supervisor comments

*Give references to potential end users in interview section.
Add screenshot of the survey questions and graph of the answers. Add implementation regarding the project.
Add more project features in unique selling point. Add your system in overall comparison table.*

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: *Pritisha* Date: *10/15/2020*

Supervisor Signature: *Sagar Khadgi* Date: *10/15/2020*

8.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: Pritisha	Surname: Tuladhar
Student Number: 2040265	Supervisor: Sagat Khadgi
Project Title: College Management Information System .	
Month: December	
What have you done since the last meeting	
Discussed about the progress of system and report. Added comparison table in literature review analysis. Completed front end of the system.	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
Send video of the system, work on user management system.	
Supervisor comments	
Work on the system and report side by side.	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: Pritisha Date: 12/04/2020
Supervisor Signature: Sagat Khadgi Date: 12/04/2020

9.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: Pritisha	Surname: Tuladhar
Student Number: 2040265	Supervisor: Sagat Khadge
Project Title: college Management Information System	Month: January
What have you done since the last meeting	
Discussed about the progress of system and report. Working on attendance management system.	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
Send video of the system, complete attendance management system, leave management system. (Previous Meetings Agenda) ???	
Supervisor comments	
Almost half of the system development must be completed before next meeting.	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: Pritisha

Date: 01/15/2021

Supervisor Signature: Sagat Khadge

Date: 01/15/2021

10.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: <i>Pritisha</i>	Surname: <i>Tuladhar</i>
Student Number: <i>2040265</i>	Supervisor: <i>Sagar Khadgi</i>
Project Title: <i>College Management Information System</i>	Month: <i>January</i>
What have you done since the last meeting	
<i>Discussed about the progress of system and report . Completed attendance management system .</i>	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
<i>Send video of the system. Work on the report .</i>	
Supervisor comments	
<i>Work on system development and features of the system .</i>	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: *Pritisha* Date: *01/22/2021*

Supervisor Signature: *Sagar Khadgi* Date: *01/22/2021*

11.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: Pritisha	Surname: Tuladhar
Student Number: 2040265	Supervisor: Sagat Khadgi
Project Title: College Management Information System . Month: February	
What have you done since the last meeting	
Discussed about the progress of system and college timetable for physical meeting. Working on leave and feedback management system .	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
Work on system development along with report .	
Supervisor comments	
Rs Research about the logic to connect to parents' panel and AI of the project .	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: Pritisha

Date: 02/15/2021

Supervisor Signature: Sagat Khadgi

Date: 02/15/2021

12.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: Pritisha	Surname: Tuladhar
Student Number: 2040265	Supervisor: Sagar Khadgi
Project Title: College Management Information System	Month: March
What have you done since the last meeting	
Completed feedback management system and leave management system.	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
Research and start working on chatbot.	
Supervisor comments	
Work on report and chatbot as well. Work on Details feedback as well.	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: Pritisha Date: 03/5/21
Supervisor Signature: Sagar Khadgi Date: 03/5/21

13.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: Pritisha F	Surname: Tuladhar
Student Number: 2040265	Supervisor: Sagar Khadgi
Project Title: College Management Information System	Month: March
What have you done since the last meeting	
Trained chatbot and made GUI of the chatbot.	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
Make API for the chatbot and implement the chatbot on the system.	
Supervisor comments	
Train more datasets and give more details on the dataset of the chatbot.	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: Pritisha F

Date: 03/26/2021

Supervisor Signature: Sagar Khadgi

Date: 03/26/2021

14.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: <i>Pritisha</i>	Surname: <i>Tuladhar</i>
Student Number: <i>2040265</i>	Supervisor: <i>Sagar Khadgi</i>
Project Title: <i>College Management Information System</i>	Month: <i>April</i>
What have you done since the last meeting	
<i>Trained chatbot, working on the report writing (artefacts, wire frames)</i>	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
<i>Complete report draft. Implement chatbot in the system.</i>	
Supervisor comments	
<i>Work the on the final report draft. Complete the features of the system. Implement chatbot on the system</i>	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: *Pritisha* Date: *04/04/2021*
Supervisor Signature: *Sagar Khadgi* Date: *04/04/2021*

15.

Faculty of Science and Engineering
School of Mathematics and Computer Science

PROJECT MANAGEMENT LOG	
First Name: <i>Pritisha</i>	Surname: <i>Tuladhak</i>
Student Number: <i>2040265</i>	Supervisor: <i>Sagar Khadgi</i>
Project Title: <i>College Management Information System</i> Month: <i>April</i>	
What have you done since the last meeting	
<i>Trained chatbot, working on literature review. Adding research paper in similar system of the chatbot.</i>	
What do you aim to complete before the next meeting	
<i>Implement chatbot on the system. Complete report draft and professionalism.</i>	
Supervisor comments	
<i>Improve UI of the system. Improve the points in the professionalism report. Try to add research paper only in the report.</i>	

We confirm that the information given in this form is true, complete, and accurate.

Student Signature: *Pritisha* Date: *04/09/2021*

Supervisor Signature: *Sagar Khadgi* Date: *04/09/2021*

8.2 Gantt Chart

Figure 125: Gantt Chart

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10. Appendices

10.1 Potential end users (Survey)

A questionnaire survey was conducted via google forms to figure out the clients or potential end users of the college management information system. It was found that most of the student having 15-26 age group mostly use the management information system of their respective school/college. From the survey, the targeted users or potential users of college management information system are students, teachers, researchers, and developers. 87.5% of people thinks that parent panel will help parents to their children academic progress. 62.5% of the total people use management information system in their laptop/pc whereas rest uses mobile phone. (Shrestha, et al., 2020)

The image shows a Google Form titled "College Management Information System Survey". The form includes a title, a subtitle, and several questions with input fields and radio button options.

College Management Information System Survey
This survey is taken for research purpose only. Please do fill the form.

Name *
Short answer text

Age *
Short answer text

Occupation *
Short answer text

School/College Name
Short answer text

Have you ever used school/college management system before? *

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

Do you think it is necessary to develop school/college management system? *

- Yes
- No

Which device do you prefer using school/college management information system? *

- Laptop/PC
- Mobile phones

Which kind of system management do you prefer? *

- Simple, easy to operate
- Complex but complete function

What performance do you think is necessary to equip the system? *

- Search quickly
- Humanized operation
- High safety
- Other...

College management information system is useful for studying/teaching? *

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Figure 126: Survey Questions 1

What do you think which functions need in the system? (Choose at least three) *

- Course arrangement
- View attendance
- Leave apply
- Information/notice announcement
- E-library
- Download student information
- Fees details
- Assignment details
- Exam result
- Other...

Parents panel will help parents to know their children academic progress.

Strongly agree
 Agree
 Neutral
 Disagree
 Strongly disagree

Suggestion regarding college management information system.

Long answer text

Figure 127: Survey Questions 2

Figure 128: Graph of age and occupation

Figure 129: Graph on school/college name and pie chart of system used before

Figure 130: Pie chart on importance of system and preferred device

Figure 131: Pie chart on system preference and performance necessity

Figure 132: Pie chart on usefulness of system and bar graph of functions

Figure 133: Review on parents' panel and suggestions

10.2 User Manual

Login:

- There are three panel in this system. They are admin panel, teacher panel and student panel.
- For logging in admin has to add user though its panel specifying as teacher or student. One can login by filling in email address and password.

Reset Password:

- In login page there is reset password function. After clicking on reset password user has to type in its email address.
- An email is sent to the email with a link to change password. User has to click on that link is redirected to reset password page.
- While giving the password, the password should not be similar to the username, should have more than 8 characters, should not be too common.
- After that the user has to confirm its password.

Adding users through admin panel:

- From add teacher page admin can add teacher.
- Unique email address must be given as the system checks the availability of the username.
- Session year, course and subject can be added. Admin can view the subject and course through manage section.
- At the left corner there is an edit button through which subject and course can be updated.
- While adding subject, a teacher must be assigned to each section.
- From add student page admin can add student. Unique email address must be given as the system checks the availability of the username.
- While adding student, course must be assigned to each student.
- From manage teacher and manage student section in admin panel, admin can update teacher and student information.

Profile:

- By clicking on the username in top of the sidebar user can view its profile. User can change its detail and password through it if needed.

Take attendance:

- Teacher can take students attendance through take attendance section in the sidebar.
- First the teacher must select the subject and session year and click on fetch student.
- The student assigned to particular subject and session year is displayed.
- By clicking on checkbox one can present the students and save attendance.
- To view the attendance taken one should fetch attendance through subject, session year and attendance date. One can update the student attendance as well.

View Attendance:

- Student can view one's attendance through view attendance section. Student has to full in the subject name along with the date from which they want to view the attendance (start date and end date).
- After clicking on fetch student, attendance data is displayed. Green color denotes present and red color denotes absent.
- Admin can also view attendance through its panel and track student's attendance.
- After clicking on view attendance, admin has to select subject, session year and attendance date and fetch student's attendance.

Apply for leave:

- There is leave apply section in teacher and student panel. User can type in date and reason for leave and apply for it.
- The leave is shown in the history with pending status on it.

Approve/disapprove leave:

- Admin can view the leave applied by teacher through teacher leave section and leave applied by student through student leave section.
- There is approve and disapprove button on the right side through which admin can approve/disapprove the leave applied by teacher.
- After admin approve/disapprove leave, the pending status in student/teacher panel is changed to approve/disapprove.

Send feedback message:

- Through teacher and student panel feedback message can be sent. After sending the message it is displayed in the history.
- The reply section is shown empty unless admin replied to the feedback message.

Reply Feedback:

- Admin can view the feedback message sent by teacher through teacher feedback section and feedback message sent by student through student feedback section.
- Admin can reply message by clicking on reply button at the right side of the message. The message replied is displayed in their respective panel.

Add result:

- Teacher can add student result by clicking on add result section in the sidebar.
- To fetch student, subject and session year must be selected and then choose the student's name from the list and fill in exam marks and assignment marks.
- From the edit result section teacher can edit student result.

View result:

- Student can view their result by clicking on view result from the side bar.
- If the mark is greater than 40 pass status is shown in green color otherwise fail status is shown in red color.

Add fee:

- Admin can add student fee through add fee section.
- To fetch the student admin has to select course and session year. Student list is displayed and admin can insert the fee amount, given date and due date.

View fee:

- Student can view their fee details from fee status in the sidebar of student panel.

Chatbot:

- User has to click on the message icon in the login page. Chat box is displayed and user has to type in the queries and send it to get replies.

10.3 GitHub log

GitHub repository link:

<https://github.com/T-Pritishaa0/FinalYearProject>

